

Effects of Workforce Diversity on Employees' Performance in Stallion Group of Company

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Abstract

It is generally recognized that there is diversity in the workforce of any enterprise, be it business, government, or civil society. This study therefore seeks to find out the effect of workforce diversity towards employee performance in Stallion Group of Companies. The Study adopted a descriptive and explanatory research design. The study population consisted of all staff of Stallion group Ltd. sample size of 80 respondents was selected and data collection method was applied by use of questionnaire, where by analysis of descriptive and inferential statistics of SPSS version 20.0 was adopted. The Pearson's correlation coefficient signifies, there is a relationship between each independent variables and the dependent variable and tested at 1% significance level. It also revealed that gender; age, ethnicity and educational background are positively correlated and the strength of the relationship is small but definite relationship to employee performance. The regression analysis shows that, the R² figure of the four independent variables is 0.211. These also mean that independent variables (gender, age, ethnicity and educational background) can explain only 21.1% of the variation in dependent variable (employee performance). However, it still leaves 78.9% unexplained in this research. In other words, there are other additional variables that are important in explaining employee performance that have not been considered in this research. It is recommended that company managements must use good strategies to effectively manage workforce diversity and collaborative research efforts should be done to ascertain the contextual variables that moderate workforce diversity to produce positive performance outcomes.

Keywords: Age, Educational background, Employee performance, Ethnicity, Gender, workforce diversity

1.0 Introduction

The need for Nigeria organization to pay attention to diversity has become necessary because of challenges of diversity in work place. Ogendengbe & Rebman (2012), posit that the way of doing things in one culture may not always be the same in another country. Hence, what is good in one culture may be bad in another. Ewanlen et al (2012). Besides, understanding the impacts of diversity on organizational outcomes, such as organizational performance, employee satisfaction, and turnover, has become essential (Sungjoo and Rainey, 2010). When the trend of diversity were first identified in the mid-1980s, they were proclaimed as an opportunity for organizations to become more creative, to reach previously untapped markets, and in general to achieve and maintain a competitive advantage. Loriann and Carol, 2007; posit that employee diversity encompasses a wide variety of differences, including work experience, parental status, educational background, geographic location, and much more. Managing diversity means more than simply observing legal and policy requirements. It also means actively promoting community and comfort with difference, Erasmus (2007) mentioned that diversity management and workforce diversity is a forced integration that creates conflict and uncertainty in the workforce as leadership is not skilled in the discipline of diversity management and its principles. As a result, managers do not know how to effectively practice diversity management, and what factors contribute to effective diversity management and task that can deal with diversity related issues in the work place. Even

though companies train employees upon hire, conduct ethics test, online training and targeted anti-harassment training, employees still make decisions to break the rules with their behavior when it comes to diversity (Victoria and Mary, 2010). Today's workforce is getting more and more heterogeneous in terms of culture due to the effects of globalization (Kurtulus, 2012). In the past twenty years, the growing diverse work force in organizations has led scholars to pay increased attention to the issue of workforce diversity (Gupta, 2013). Ewanlen et al (2012). Further asserts that cultural differences do affect managerial behaviour and practices such as planning, organizing, staffing and controlling. In line with this view Dasanyaka and Mahakalanda (2008) note that there is greater need to adapt to external and internal changes of

organizational culture because it has become imperative today as the world is moving towards knowledge based economy.

Statement of the Problem

Gender of workforce in organization has been of contention in relation to nature of jobs, as advancement of liberalization age, men and women are now given educational and equal employment opportunity and women are also attributed to be part of economic market also. Kochan et.al (2002) Second, several researchers have opined that how organizations approach age diversity can have significant implications for whether the organization is helped or harmed by its diversity (Ely & Thomas, 2001). Diversity within an organisation according to Dahm (2003) can invoke an array of emotions. Some researchers view diversity as a menace that requires hard measures of management. Ugwuzor, (2014) states that research shows that various types of team and organisational age diversity sometimes increase conflict, reduce social cohesion, and increase employee turnover. Therefore, the main focus of the study was to identify the effects of workforce diversity by creating a relationship among gender, age, ethnicity, and education background towards employees' performance in Stallion Group Ltd. This study examined the following specific research questions:

- i. How does gender diversity affect employee performance?
 - ii. What is the effect of age diversity on employee performance?
 - iii. What is the effect of ethnicity diversity on employee performance?
- Iv. To what extent does educational background influence employee performance

To this end, the hypothesis of the study reflects employee performance is the dependent variable while gender, age, and education background are the independent variables. Four hypotheses were tested:

Hypothesis 1

Ho₁: There is no effect of gender diversity on employees' performance.

Hypothesis 2

Ho₂: There is no effect of age diversity on employees' performance.

Hypothesis 3

Ho₃: There is no effect ethnicity diversity on employees' performance

Hypothesis 4

Ho₄: There no effect of educational background on employee performance

2.0 Review of Literature

Conceptual Framework

Concept of Employee Diversity

After decades of talking about diversity in the workplace, there is still considerable debate and confusion over what actually constitutes workforce diversity, (Simons & Rowland, 2011). Workforce diversity is generally viewed as acknowledging, understanding, accepting, valuing, and celebrating differences among people with respect to age, class, ethnicity, gender, physical and mental ability, race, sexual orientation, spiritual practice, and public assistance status. Diversity refers to a mosaic of people who bring a variety of backgrounds, perspectives, values, and benefits as assets to the groups and organizations with which they interact (Otikey, Messah, & Mwaleka, 2010). Mulkeen,(2008) describes workplace diversity as all the differences that exist within people with respect to age, gender, sexual orientation, education, cultural background, religion, and work experience. Valuing diversity is a key component of effective people management, which can improve workplace productivity (Black & Enterprise, (2001). Dessler, (2011) defines diversity as the variety or multiplicity of demographic features that characterize a company's workforce, particularly in terms of race, sex, culture, national origin, handicap, age, and religion. Jones & George (2011), assert that diversity is differences among people in age, gender, race, ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, socioeconomic background, and capabilities/disabilities. Currently, the case of diversity is enjoying high profile in organizational debate partly due to changes in workforce demographics (Armstrong & Mkamwa, 2010). Gupta, (2013) argues that overall workforce diversity enhances better decision making, higher creativity, innovation, and greater competitive advantage. Armstrong, (2006) states that managing diversity is about ensuring that all people maximize their potential and their contribution to

the organization. Wentling & Palmarivas, (2000) defines workforce diversity as including cultural factors such as race, gender, age, color, physical ability, ethnicity etc. The broader definition of diversity may include age, national origin, religion, disability, sexual orientation, values, ethnic culture, education, language, lifestyle, beliefs, physical appearance, and economic status (Wentling & Palmarivas, 2000). The term diversity is used to illustrate how individuals differ by gender, ethnicity, age, physical abilities, lifestyle, and religion. Workplace diversity incorporates the meaning of diversity within a workplace setting. (Elsaid, 2012).

Today, organizations are embracing a more inclusive definition of diversity that recognizes a spectrum of differences that influence how employees approach work, interact with each other or derive satisfaction from work, (Daft, Kendrick & Natalia, 2010). Okoro et al, (2012) state that recruitment, management and maintenance of a diverse workforce ensures that the right combination of skills and competencies are available in an organization. Demographic diversity refers to the degree to which a business unit (e.g a work group or organization is heterogeneous with respect to demographic attributes such as age, sex & tenure (Sungjoo, & Rainy, 2009). Today, organizations are embracing a more inclusive definition of diversity that recognizes a spectrum of differences that influence how employees approach work,

interact with each other or derive satisfaction from work, (Daft, Kendrick & Natalia, 2010). Okoro et al, (2012) state that recruitment, management and maintenance of a diverse workforce ensures that the right combination of skills and competencies are available in an organization. Demographic diversity refers to the degree to which a business unit (e.g a work group or organization is heterogeneous with respect to demographic attributes such as age, sex & tenure (Sungjoo, & Rainy, 2009). Social cultural diversity on the other hand refers to attributes such as race, ethnicity, religion or sexual orientation. Workforce diversity has evolved from a focus on legally protected human attributes such as race, gender and age to a much broader definition that includes the entire spectrum of human differences among employees in terms of age, cultural background, physical abilities and disabilities, race, religion, sex and sexual orientation (Jayne & Dipboye, 2004).

Theoretical Framework

Age Diversity

Social Identity and Self-Categorization

Possible explanations for negative effects of age diversity can be derived from the concept of compositional demography, which draws heavily on theories of social identity and self categorization. This theory suggests that individuals tend to classify themselves and others into certain groups on the basis of dimensions that are personally relevant for them. These dimensions often include demographic categories such as gender, age, or ethnicity (Kunze et al., 2009; Tajfel and Turner, 1986). According to social identity theory, social identity and intergroup behavior are guided by the pursuit of evaluative positive social identity; through positive intergroup distinctiveness, which in turn, is motivated by the need for positive self-esteem (Hogg and Terry, 2000; Abrams and Hogg, 1988)

Ethnicity Diversity

Sprainer, Dreachslin, and Hunt (2000) found out in visual representation of the resultant theoretical model of how race influences the self-perceived communication effectiveness of nursing care teams. It should be noted that, irrespective of team role or race, NCT members were generally dissatisfied with the effectiveness of team communication. According to Sprainer et al. (2000), the NCT members who did characterize communication within their own NCT saw their team's performance as not representative and acknowledged that communication within other NCTs was often fraught with conflict and misunderstanding. Based on Sprainer et al. (2000) study, effective communication, widely recognized as key to high performing teams occur when sender and receiver share a common interpretation of the communication exchange; example, when the intended message and the received message are Sprainer et al. (2000) study stated that unifies racially and ethnically diverse groups and, thereby, enables teamwork. Although communication as an integrating mechanism appears to be central to well-functioning racially and ethnically diverse teams, the process of

communication in racially and ethnically diverse teams has not been the focus of group or team research. (Maznevski, 1994). According to Sprainer et al. (2000) it is stated that the purpose of the reanalysis was to develop a grounded theory of the role that race plays in the self-perceived communication effectiveness of nursing care teams.

Educational background

Conscientiousness

Barrick and Mount (1993) described those high in conscientiousness as ideal employees because these individuals possess, responsible, dependable, persistent, and achievement oriented traits. Conscientiousness employees tend to be ambitious, exacting, methodical, and disciplined, whereas individuals low in conscientiousness tend to be imprecise, impetuous, and disorganized (Gellatly, 1996). Conscientious individuals are expected to perform at a higher level because they are, by predisposition, more persevering and disciplined (Colquitt and Simmering, 1998), as well as more confident in their abilities (Barrick and Mount, 1991). As such, they are likely more effective in identifying key priorities and contributing activities that support organizational objectives. Significant evidence indicates that the conscientiousness; performance association is augmented in the presence of certain moderating variables. For example, studies have demonstrated the utility of including autonomy (Gellatly and Irving, 2001), organizational politics, agreeableness (Witt, Burke, Barrick, and Mount, 2002), and extraversion (Witt, 2002) as intervening factors. However, in the search for moderators, a significant concern related to unexpected inverse relationships between conscientiousness and performance has surfaced (Driskell, Hogan, Salas, and Hoskitt, 1994). As a result, the continued search for appropriate moderating variables is necessary to further supplement our knowledge and provide insight into the conscientiousness–performance relationship.

Gender Diversity

The increase in gender diversity at the workplace has attracted the attention of both researchers and practitioners and a particular question that arise is whether gender composition in an organizations' workforce will affect individual, group or organizational level performance (Gupta, 2013). Due to rapid environmental changes, many countries are changing to accommodate the increasing diverse workforce in their organizations, (Elsaid, 2012). Several researchers investigating workforce diversity have found that gender diversity in the boardroom can positively affect firm performance (Carter, Simkins & Simpson 2003,). However, other studies have reported contrary findings of a negative relationship between women in boards and firm performance (Dwyer, Richard & Chandwick, 2003) while (Dimovski & Brooks, 2006) reported no direct relationship between gender diversity and firm performance. Several researchers have argued that high levels of gender diversity are a source of competitive advantage. Based on literature, we argue that a well-balanced gender composition of employees may help create synergy leading to positive organization outcomes. Gender diversity is associated with resources that can provide a firm with a sustained competitive advantage. These resources include market insight, creativity, innovation and improved problem solving capabilities (Nkomo & Cox, 1993). Men's and Women's differences may provide insights into the different needs of male and female customers. Researchers have further argued that men and women may also have different cognitive abilities. A combination of different cognitive abilities in a gender diverse team may enhance overall team cohesion, creativity, and innovation leading to improved organizational performance.

Workforce Diversity Management

Carrell (2006) defines workforce diversity as the ways that people differ which can affect a task or relationship within an organization such as age, gender, race, education, religion, and culture. Chatman and Spataro (2005) rightly note that there are a number of activities that an organization can engage in to manage the diversity of their workforce. Carrell (2006) comments in Labor Law Journal that although workforce diversity has become a reality in organizations today as predicted by Workforce 2000 in a 1987 report by the Hudson Institute, the ways that organizations define and manage workforce diversity are still evolving. The increasing trend of workforce diversity along racial, ethnic and gender lines, as well as an increasing percentage of the workforce that is below the age of 30 and over the age 55 have several implications for HRD professionals, employees and company in general. This arises out of the prejudices that may persist, cultural insensitivity and language differences, increasing numbers of women in the workforce and the aging of the workforce. Although this research discussed the impacts of workforce diversity on employee performance, it is good to note that diversity and equality are two concomitant principles just like time and space. Skaggs and Ditomaso (2004) argue that to understand the impact of workforce diversity, scholars must consider the effects of the distribution of valued and scarce resources, the relationships among people and groups, and the compositional effects of the unit such as job, occupation, firm, or society. These have

significance on allocation decisions and evaluative processes that then lead to labor force outcomes like attitudes, behaviors, and material and psychic rewards. Although scholars in this field provide some insight into the broader picture of workplace inequality, there still remains a great need to understand the mechanisms through which workforce diversity yields differential consequences within work groups, jobs, occupations, firms, and even societies. Contemporary trends in the legal framework have necessitated the putting in place specific statutes making it unlawful to discriminate on grounds such as sex, marital status, race, national origin, ethnicity, disability, sexual orientation, religion or belief, union membership or non-membership, part-time or full time workers, or ex-offenders whose convictions are spent (Torrington et al., 2005). Torrington (2005) continues to argue that equal pay law requires men and women to be paid the same wage for doing work which is the same or which can be shown to be of equal value unless the employer can justify a difference on grounds other than sex. There are different approaches to equality such as legislative action/the equal opportunities or liberal approach and the managing diversity (Ford, 1996). According to Homana, Barber and Purta (2005) positive work climate includes an identifiable, open and nurturing school ethos that foster a sense of responsibility, achievement, commitment and efficacy among staff and students. It is also characterized by a commitment to organizational achievement and development of students, mutual respect and collaboration among the head and staff. Bahamon (2002) posits that positive work climate has been identified as a driver of performance and contributes a third of an organizational results. The responsibility of creating work climate lies solely on the head of the institution whose behaviour determines the work climate. The positive behavior drives the work climate which arouses motivation and the aroused motivation is a major driver of bottom-line performance. To create a positive work climate, the leaders of the organization must work with staff in order to manage diversity as to foster and sustain staff motivation. Graen (2003) cites other sources of diversity as political favoritism, family connections, educational advantage, friendships, and Leader Member Exchange partnering skills including performance on team skills. Thompson and Ditomasso in Ellis and Sonnenfield (1994) also argue that a multicultural management perspective fosters more innovative and creative decision making, satisfying work environments, and better products because all people who have a contribution to make are encouraged to be involved in a meaningful way this in turn yields more information, more points of view, more ideas and fewer reservations. According to D'Netto and Sohal (1999), organizations which plan for the anticipated workforce and accept cultural diversity management as a progressive technique will benefit from better employee retention, increased productivity, less absenteeism, better morale, an expanded marketplace and improved customer service (Manning *et al.*, 1996). The desired outcomes include attracting and developing the best employees which should give the organization a competitive edge to generate greater profits that support job security. Due to the fact that employees can understand how these outcomes are desirable, they will support the organization's efforts at managing diversity and embrace a culture that supports diversity (Carrel, 2006). The increased diversity in the workplace converges with the increased use of teams in the workplace through clusters of attributes like personal demographics; knowledge, skills, and abilities; values, beliefs, and attitudes; personality and cognitive and behavioral style; and organizational demographics. Diversity recognizes the unique barriers of race and gender among others while at the same time creating a work environment that values the diversity

Employee Performance

Previous research on workplace diversity suggests that diversity can be either detrimental or beneficial for employee performance (Williams and O'Reilly, 1998). For instance, employee diversity is positively associated with creativity and problem-solving skills (Bantel and Jackson, 1989; Jehn et al., 1999) and negatively related with cohesiveness and cooperation (Pelled et al., 1999). Good work force diversity practices in the area of human resources are believed to enhance both employee and organizational performance (Adler, 1986). Furthermore, employee diversity allows increased creativity, a wider range of perspectives, better problem definition, more alternatives and better solutions (Adler, 1986). It is also argued that with decreasing homogeneity in the workforce, it has become crucial for organizations to develop equal opportunities and diversity management policies to maintain the skills of employees with diverse backgrounds in order to protect their competitive position in the market place (Gilbert and Ivancevich, 2000; Shaw, 1993). Work place diversity generates conflicts between employees. Conflict occurs due to differences of perception, ideas, behaviors, interest, attitudes, religious differences, political differences and unjustified distribution of resources. Conflict is not always negative and does not always create hostilities. It

very much depends on how the conflict is handled. If handled properly, it can become a very rich source of development (Kigali, 2006). When corporate managers ignore the conflicts between co-workers, this will result in clashes amongst them. In turn, these clashes will be converted into personal and emotional conflict in the long run and therefore damages the organizational culture, worker morale, and overall organizational performance. It can also lead to a reduction in creativity, innovation, quality, and performance of employees and organizations ultimately leading to negative effects on the team performance (Jehn, 1994, 1995; Amason, 1996; De Dreu and Vande, 1997; Friedman et al., 2000; Michael et al., 2001; Passos and Caetano, 2005). ployees bring to the organization.

3.0 Methodology

The research design type is descriptive and explanatory research that describes characteristics of objects, people, groups, organizations, or environments. This study focuses on investigating and examining the effects of workforce diversity towards employees' performances in Stallion Group. In this research, questionnaire survey was chosen as a tool to examine the factors that affect employees' performances in Stallion Group. The reason of using questionnaire is to ensure completeness and consistency of information gathered. The targeted population size for the study that was undertaken by the researcher for which questionnaire were distributed, there are 301 grand total populations as of April 30, 2014. To obtain information relevant to the study both primary and secondary data were used. The method employed to get primary information was a well-designed questionnaire distributed to the selected sample population. Therefore, data collected through the questionnaire were analyzed statistically by using the Software Package for Social Science (SPSS Version 20.0). Besides, it also enables to present the data or information better through tabular presentation). SPSS was also used to test the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variable using methods such as Pearson Correlation analysis and Multiple Regression analysis. The data gathered through primary methods were summarized. Hypothesis findings of this research were evaluated using Software Package for Social Science (SPSS) to determine whether the hypothesis is supported by the research

4.0 Data analysis and Hypothesis Testing

Demographic characteristics of the respondents based on frequency analysis.

Gender

Table 1: Gender of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	51	63.
Female	29	36.3
Total	80	100

Source: Research Survey, 2018

Table 1, shows a percentage of respondents, whereby female (36.25%), while male (63.75%). In other words, from the 80 respondents, 51 of them are male while the remaining 29 are female

Age

Table 2: Age of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percent
20-29 years old	9	11.3
30-39 years old	42	52.5
40-49 years old	24	30
50 years old and above	5	6.3
Total	80	100

Source: Research Survey, 2018

Table 2 shows age group of the respondents. The majority of the respondents fall under the age group category of 30 - 39 years old (accounted for 52.5% or 42 respondents), followed by the age group of 40 - 49 years old (30% or 24 respondents), 20 - 29 years old (11.25% or 9 respondents), and 50 years old and above (6.25% or 5 respondents). As a result, individuals tend to favor members of their own group at the expenses of the other groups, against which they may discriminate. Consequently, if the employees age or generational belonging is regarded as a relevant criterion for distinction, a differentiation between age

groups within an organization may emerge, fostering emotional conflicts and age based discrimination between the age groups.

Nationality

Table 3: Ethnicity of the Respondents

Nationality	Frequency	Percent
YORUBA	76	95
IBO	2	2.5
INDIANS	2	2.5
Total	80	100

Source: Research Survey, 2018

Table 3 shows that the highest proportion of respondents are Yoruba (95% or 76 respondents), followed by IBO and INDIANS (5% or 4 respondents), this is because, all the foreigners are department managers.

Educational Background

Table 4: Educational Level of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent
Diploma	12	15.00
Degree	61	76.25
Master	7	8.75
Total	80	100

Source: Research Survey, 2018

Table 4 shows the educational level of the respondents. The majority of the respondents are degree holders (76.25% or 61 respondents), followed by diploma holders (15% or 12 respondents), masters (8.75% or 7 respondents). Most respondents are degree holders, because there are a lot of degree holders in the labor market.

Working Experience

Table 8: Working Experience of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent
2-5 years	18	22.50
6-10 years	15	18.75
10- 15 years	23	28.75
More than 15 years	24	30.00
Total	80	100.0

Source: Research Survey, 2018

Employees who are managers with higher education and the staff whose length of service is more than 10 year’s shows unusual decline in work performance because they have not found the suitable development space, so temporary disengagement happens.

Position Level

Table 9: Position Level of the Respondents in the company.

Frequency	Percent
Department Manager	3 3.75
Division Manager	17 21.25
Warehouse Manager	14 17.50
Civil /Mechanical Engineer	8 10.00
Lubricant Engineer	6 7.50
Store keepers	9 11.25
IT Specialist	3 3.75
Accountant	11 13.75
Others(Admin assistants and coldroom staffs)	9 11.25
Total	80 100.00

Source: Own Survey generated by SPSS version 20.0

Majority of the respondents are Division Managers (21.5% or 17 respondents), followed by Territory Managers (17.5% or 14 respondents), Department Managers are (3.75% or 3 respondents) and others as indicated in the table above.

Central Tendencies Measurement of Constructs

Measurement of central tendencies is used to discover the mean scores for the five interval scaled constructs. A total of 39 items (questions) with particular mean score were obtained from the SPSS output. All of the items/questions are being asked using 5-point Likert scale with 1 indicating strongly disagree, 2 indicating disagree, 3 indicating neutral, 4 indicating agree, and 5 indicating strongly agree.

The Effects of Gender on employee Performance.

Majority of the respondents (26.3%) disagreed that he/she have been discriminated by employer while hiring and recruitment process, while 23.8% of them neither agreed nor disagreed with that statement. 41.3% of the respondents agreed that they feel the organization does a good job of attracting and hiring women, while 37.5% of them neither agreed nor disagreed with that statement. Meanwhile, 48.8% of the respondents agreed that fair treatment is given to all employees whether they are male or female, while 10% of them neither agreed nor disagreed with that statement. 45% of the respondents agreed and 25% of them neither agreed nor disagreed that opportunities for growth and advancement exist for women in our organization. For the question career development that includes women is encouraged within our Company which is 37.5% respondent agree and 27.5% of them neither agreed nor disagreed and 22.5% disagree on this statement. For the next question, the company's training and development program is developed to meet the criteria/requirement of performed by male and female employees, there is 46.3% of respondent agree and 23.8% of them neither agreed nor disagreed. 48.8% of respondents agreed that women are involved in the company's decision making as much as men, while 11.3% of them neither agreed nor disagreed and 25.3% disagree on this statement. 41.3% of respondents disagreed that the performance criteria for success are expected to be higher for man than for women, while 23.8% neither agreed nor disagreed. Finally, 61.3% of the respondents agreed that they are positive about gender diversity in this workplace, while 13.8% of them neither agreed nor disagreed with this statement. "I am positive about gender diversity in this workplace" is the item with highest mean (mean=3.91), followed by "Fair treatment (the same compensation, benefits and opportunities, based on their skill) is given to all employees, whether they are male or female" with mean 3.74. The item with third highest mean is "Opportunities for growth and advancement exist for women employees in our company" with mean 3.46. I see value in gender-diversity initiatives and also I believe that the company does a good job of attracting and hiring women employees and Women are involved in the company's decision making as much as men" with both mean 3.29. "The performance criteria for success are expected to be higher for men than for women." Has the lowest mean among the others (mean =2.56). The item "The Company prefers to hire male workers compared with women because they are perceived to have better performance and ability to manage their jobs." has the highest standard deviation, which is 1.249. The item with second highest standard deviation is "Women are involved in the company's decision making.

The Effects of age on employee Performance

There were as much as 48.8% of the respondents agreed that the organization provides them with equal opportunities for training and career development, while 16.3.3% of them neither agreed nor disagreed with that statement. 26.3% of the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed that their team leaders include all members at different ages in problem solving and decision making, while 55% of them agreed. Both questions which are "the age differences in work group might the performance of employees" and "at work, I experience lack of bonding with people of different age group" have 32.5% and 61.3% of the respondents disagreed respectively and 33.8% and 21.3% of them neither agreed nor disagreed% with the statement respectively. "I am positive about age diversity in this place" is the item with highest mean (mean=3.91), followed by "My team leaders include all members at different ages in problem solving and decision making" (means = 3.60). The item with the lowest mean is "At work, I experience lack of bonding with people of different age group." (Mean=2.55). The items "the age differences in work group might cause conflict" and "at work, I experience lack of bonding with people of different age group" have the highest

standard deviation, which is 1.152 and 1.066 respectively. The item with lowest standard deviation is “I am positive about age diversity in this workplace”, with the standard deviation value of 0.7325.

The Effects of Ethnicity on employee performance

Most of the respondents (23.8%) disagreed and 56.3% of them neither agreed nor disagreed that the organization does a good job of attracting and hiring minorities. 25.0% of the respondents agreed and 43.8% of them neither agreed nor disagreed and strongly agreed that they have an opportunities for growth and advancement exist for minorities in their organization. Most of the respondents (46.3%) agreed that the organization concerns about the employees customs, cultures and values and 46.3% of the respondents strongly disagree on the statement “at work, I developed low self-esteem due to my ethnicity” and “The team leader includes all members at different ethnicity in problem solving and decision making” have the result 47.5% agreed and 32.5% neither agreed nor disagreed on the statements. “I am positive about ethnicity diversity in this workplace” is the item with highest mean (mean = 4.05), followed by “The ethnicity differences in educational background do not affect employee performance (means = 3.79). The item with the lowest mean is “At work, I developed low self esteem due to my ethnicity” (mean = 1.83). The item that has the highest standard deviation (1.041) is “Different languages that are used to communicate do not create problem among employees”. The items “The ethnicity differences in educational background do not affect employee performance”, “At work, I developed low self-esteem due to my ethnicity” and “Opportunities for growth and advancement exist for minorities in our company ” have the second ,third and fourth highest standard deviation, which is 0.999,0.965 and 0.952 respectively. The item “The Company does a good job of attracting and hiring minorities” has the lowest standard deviation (0.792).

The Effects of Educational background on employee performance

There were as much as 61.3% of the respondents agreed and 13.8% neither agreed nor disagreed that the recruitment plan of the organization is based on the education background of the employees and also get the same result for the question “the difference in education background does not encourage conflict”. 45.0% of the respondents agreed and 51.3% also agreed that the organization provides paid study leave to employees who need supplementary education. 30.0% of the respondents agreed and 27.5% of them neither agreed nor disagreed that “Opportunities for growth and advancement exist for employees who have lower qualification in education”, while 30% of them disagreed with that statement. 51.3% of the respondent disagreed and 33.8% strongly disagreed that at work, they experience lack of confidence due to their educational background, while 10.0% of them agreed with that statement. 25.0% of the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed and 45.0% of them agreed that their team leader includes all members at different education level in problem solving and decision making. Finally, 23.8% of the respondents disagreed that their organization gives equal treatment when it comes to the diversity of education background, while 50.0% of them agreed with that statement. “The recruitment plan of the company is based on the educational background of the employees” is the item with the highest mean (mean=3.74), followed by “The organization provides paid study leave to employees who need supplementary education” (means = 3.55). There was 1 item with the lowest means which is “At work, I experience lack of confidence due to my educational background” with mean 1.96. The item that has the highest standard deviation (1.055) is “The difference in education background does not encourage conflict”. The item with second highest standard deviation (1.054) is “Opportunities for growth and advancement exist for employees who have lower qualification in education”. The item “The recruitment plan of the company is based on the educational background of the employees” has the lowest standard deviation (0.924)

Central tendencies Measurement of Construct: Employee Performance

There were as much as 68.8% of the respondents agreed that they enjoy their tasks and the divisions work approach while 16.3% strongly agreed with that statement. 71.3% of the respondents agreed and 33.8% of them strongly agreed and only 1.3% of them neither agreed nor disagreed that they are committed to the mission and direction of their company. There was little number of the respondents (6.3%) neither agreed nor disagreed and 51.3% of them agreed that they were motivated to complete the task that is assigned to them. 52.5% of the respondents agreed and 47.5% of them strongly agreed co-operate well with their colleagues of different ethnicity. Aggregately, more than half of the respondents (46.3% and 36.3%) agreed and strongly agreed that opposite gender can perform well and they enjoy working with them, while 8.8% of them neither agreed nor disagreed with that statement. 38.8% of the respondents agreed and 21.3% of them

neither agreed nor disagreed that their performance levels affects their salary levels. 27.5% and 33.8% of the respondents disagreed and with the statement “I am satisfied with my current salary level” respectively. Finally, there was 65% of the respondents agreed and 11.3% of them neither agreed nor disagreed that they are given the chance to try their own method of doing the job. “Good employee performance is important for the future growth of my company.” is the item with highest mean (mean=4.68), followed by “I co-operate well with my colleagues of different ethnicity” (means=4.48). The item with the lowest mean is “I am satisfied with my current salary level” (mean=3.14). The item that has the highest standard deviation (1.166) is “I am satisfied with my current salary level”. The item with second highest standard deviation (0.606) is “My performance level affects my salary level. The item “Good employee performance is important for the future growth of my company.” has the lowest standard deviation (0.497).

Correlation Analysis

Pearson’s correlation coefficient will indicate the direction, strength and significant of the bivariate relationship among all the variables that were measured at an interval or ratio level (i.e. gender, age, ethnicity and education background). The number representing the Pearson correlation is referred to as a correlation coefficient. Correlations of +1 mean that, there is a perfect relationship between two variables. Hair, Money Samouel (2007) proposed Rules of Thumb on coefficient range and strength of association .

Correlation between gender group and employee performance

Hypothesis 1

Ho₁: There is no significant effects of gender group on employees’ performance

Direction of relationship :There is positive relationship between gender group and employee performance because of the value for correlation coefficient is positive. The gender group variable has a 0.298 correlation with the employee performance variable.

Strength of relationship :The value of this correlation coefficient (0.298) is fall under coefficient range from ± 0.2 1 to ± 0.40 . Therefore, the relationship between gender group and employee performance is small but definite relationship.

Significance of relationship:The relationship between gender group and employee performance is significant. It is because the p-value 0.007 is less than alpha value 0.01. Therefore, null hypothesis (H₀) is not accepted but alternative hypothesis (H₁) is accepted.

Correlation between age group and employee performance

Hypothesis 2

Ho₂ : There is no significant effects of age group on employees’ performance.

Direction of relationship:From the table above, there is positive relationship between age group and employee performance because of the value for correlation coefficient is positive. The age group variable has a 0.000 correlation with the employee performance variable.

Strength of relationship:The value of this correlation coefficient (0.3 97) is fall under coefficient range from ± 0.2 1 to ± 0.40 . Therefore, the relationship between gender group and employee performance is small but definite relationship.

Significance of relationship:The relationship between gender group and employee performance is significant. It is because the p-value 0.000 is less than alpha value 0.01. Therefore, null hypothesis (H₀) is not accepted but alternative hypothesis (H₁) is accepted.

Correlation between ethnicity group and employee performance

Hypothesis 3

Ho₃ : There is no significant effects of ethnicity group on employees’ performance.

Direction of relationship: there is positive relationship between ethnicity group and employee performance because of the value for correlation coefficient is positive. The ethnicity group variable has a 0.346 correlation with the employee performance variable.

Strength of relationship: The value of this correlation coefficient (0.346) is fall under coefficient range from ± 0.2 1 to ± 0.40 . Therefore, the relationship between ethnicity group and employee performance is small, but definite relationship.

Significance of relationship: The relationship between ethnicity group and employee performance is significant. It is because the p-value 0.002 is less than alpha value 0.01. Therefore, null hypothesis (H0) is not accepted but alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted.

Correlation between educational group and employee performance

Hypothesis 4

Ho₄ : There is no significant effects of educational background group on employees' performance.

Direction of relationship: there is positive relationship between educational background group and employee performance because of the value for correlation coefficient is positive. The education background group variable has a 0.365 correlation with the employee performance variable.

Strength of relationship: The value of this correlation coefficient (0.365) is fall under coefficient range from ± 0.2 1 to ± 0.40 . Therefore, the relationship between educational background group and employee performance is small, but definite relationship.

Significance of relationship: The relationship between educational background group and employee performance is significant. It is because the p-value 0.001 is less than alpha value 0.01. Therefore, null hypothesis (H0) is not accepted but alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. As a result employee performance relates positively with variables such as gender, age, ethnicity and educational background, the company should start realizing the need to be tackle such demographic categories in order to stay ahead of its competitors.

Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis is a method which uses more than one independent variable to explain variance in a dependent variable.

Table 10: Model Summary of Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of Estimate
1	.460a	.211	.169	.43472

a. Predictors: (Constant), Gender, Age, Ethnicity, Education background

b. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Own Survey Data generated by SPSS version 20.0

The R value is the correlation coefficient between the dependent variable and the independent variables. According to the Model Summary, the value of correlation coefficient (R) of four independent variables (gender, age, ethnicity and educational background) with the dependent variable (employee performance) is 0.460. Therefore, there is positive and moderate correlation between four independent variable and dependent variable. Besides that, Model Summary also indicates the coefficient of determination (R square) which can help in explaining the variance. The R square figure of the four independent variables is 0.211. These also mean that independent variables (gender, age, ethnicity and educational background) can explain 21.1% of the variation in dependent variable (employee performance). However, it still leaves 78.9% (100% - 21.1%) unexplained in this research. In other words, there are other additional variables that are important in explaining employee performance that have not been considered in this research.

The four independent variables are the factors that determine perceived employability.

This can be represented by the equation as below:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 +$$

Where: Y = Dependent variable (Employee performance)

a = Constant variable

b₁ = Value of independent variable 1 (Gender)

X₁ = Independent variable 1 (Gender)

b₂ = Value of independent variable 2 (Age)

X₂ = Independent variable 2 (Age)

b₃ = Value of independent variable 3 (Ethnicity)

X3= In dependent variable 3 (Ethnicity)

b4= Value of independent variable 4 (Educational background)

X4= In dependent variable 4 (Educational Background)

Based on the Coefficients, the regression equation for the employee performance is: Employee Performance = 2.476 + (0.258) Gender Group + (0.326) Age Group Ethnicity Group + (0.313) Educational Background Group.+ (0.299) From the Coefficient's table, *age group* is the first and most significant independent variable in this research since its t-value is 3.820 and p-value is 0.000, which is lower than alpha value 0.01. This also shows that age group is significant to predict perceived employee performance. Besides that, age group is the predictor variable that contribute the highest to the variation of the perceived employee performance because Beta value (under standardized coefficients) for this predictor variable is the largest (= 0.3 97), which means a change of one standard deviation in age diversity has 3 9.7% change of standard deviation on employee performance Besides, *educational background group* is second most significant variable where it carries out the t-value 3.462 and the p-value 0.002, which is lower than the alpha value 0.01. This shows that educational background group is significant to predict perceived employee performance. In addition, ethnicity group contribute the second highest to the variation of the perceived employee performance because Beta value (under standardized coefficients) for this predictor variable is the second largest (= 0.365)), which means a change of one standard deviation in educational background diversity has 3 6.5% change of standard deviation on employee performance. The third most significant independent variable is *ethnicity group*, where the t-value is 3.252 and the p-value is 0.001, which is lower than the alpha value 0.01. This represent that the ethnicity group is significant to predict perceived employee performance. Besides, educational background group contribute the third highest to the variation of the perceived employee performance because Beta value (under standardized coefficients) for this predictor variable is the third largest (= 0.346), which means a change of one standard deviation in ethnicity diversity has 34.6% change of standard deviation on employee performance. Lastly, in this research, *gender group* is significant independent variable where it carries out the t-value 2.76 1 and the p-value 0.007, which is lower than the alpha value 0.01. This shows that gender group is significant to predict perceived employee performance. In addition, gender group contributes Beta value (under standardized coefficients) for this predictor variable is (= 0.298), which means a change of one standard deviation in gender diversity has 29.8% change of standard deviation on employee performance. The result indicates that the four independent variables (gender group, ethnicity group, education background group, and age group) have a significant relationship with the employee performance.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Result Summary of Hypotheses Testing Table 11

Hypothesis	Accepted
Rejected	
1. There is significant relationship between gender group and employee performance	=0.298 p=0.007<0.01
2. There is significant relationship between age group and employee performance	= 0.3 97 p=0.000<0.01
3. There is significant relationship between ethnicity group and employees performance	=0.346 p=0 . 002<0.01
4. There is significant relationship between educational background group and employees performance	=0.365 p=0.001<0.01

Source: Own survey generated by SPSS version 20.0

Relationship between gender group and employee performance

H1 : There is significant relationship between gender group and employee performance Based on the result from the inferential analysis, there is significant positive and small but definite relationship between gender group and employee performance which carries correlation coefficient value of 0.298 and p-value of 0.007 which is significant at the alpha value 0.01. The finding in this research showed that gender group and employee performance is positively linked. Based on the information provided in the research the overall feeling is that, for the most part, gender was not an area of concern. All divisions of the company must meet annual targets for the representation of majority and minority males and females in each employee grade level (Kochan, Bezrukova and Ely, 2002). In order to enforce the employee performance described above, performance appraisals employees included measures employee's ability to achieve the targets. According to the Kochan, Bezrukova and Ely (2002), the performance appraisals were used for making promotion and compensation related decisions. Training practices included intensive diversity training. Trainers used behavioral modeling techniques to help develop managerial capabilities for interacting with subordinates and colleagues irrespective of demographic differences. Thus the training efforts focused more on skill-building than on building awareness or modifying attitudes. Furthermore, according to the research revealed that 36.25% of female participants hold salaried positions, and men participants hold 63.75% of the salaried positions. Although there are smaller percentage of female participants in salaried positions, the number is still high compared to the norm.

Relationship between age group and employee performance

H1: There is significant relationship between age group and employee performance Based on the result from the inferential analysis, there is significant and small but definite relationship between age group and employee performance which carries correlation coefficient value of 0.397 and p-value of 0.000 which is significant at the alpha value 0.01. Age is also regularly viewed as one dimension of social category diversity (Jehn, Northcraft, and Neale (1999); Simons, Pelled, and Smith (1999); and Pelled, Eisenhardt, and Xin (1999)). However, the result shows that, there is an influence of age diversity on employee performance, which agrees to the findings of the empirical studies reviewed by Gelner and Stephen (2009) summarized that age heterogeneity can negatively affect productivity concerns differences in the values in and preferences of distinct age groups. It has been shown that productivity diminishing conflicts are particularly frequent in the presence of "generation gaps". However, Gelner and Stephen (2009) [6] also include that age heterogeneity may be placed in proximity with its potential benefits. Complementary effects emerge when collaboration in a group enables individuals to be more productive than when working on their own. Hence, the benefits of age heterogeneity are based on additional productivity effects that arise due to interaction among individuals of different ages with differing skill profiles, differing perspectives and perhaps also different personality traits.

Relationship between ethnicity group and employee performance

H1: There is significant relationship between ethnicity group and employee performance Based on the result from the inferential analysis, there is significant positive and small, but definite relationship between ethnicity group and employee performance which carries correlation coefficient value of 0.346 and p-value of 0.002 which is significant at the alpha value 0.01. Ethnically diverse teams working in relatively homogeneous organizations experienced performance deficits relative to the more homogeneous teams (Joshi and Jackson, 2003). Furthermore, the performance deficit was not evident for ethnically diverse teams working in ethnically diverse organizations. In ethnically homogeneous organizations, the ethnic differences among members of diverse teams become more salient and are more likely to interfere with performance. In ethnically heterogeneous organizations, however, the ethnic identities of team members may be less salient and therefore they create less disruption (Joshi and Jackson, 2003).

Relationship between education background group and employee performance

H1: There is significant relationship between educational background group and employee performance Based on the inferential analysis, there is significant positive and slight, almost negligible relationship between education background group and employee performance which carries correlation coefficient value of 0.365 and p-value of 0.001 which is significant at the alpha value 0.01. Different education types, or a more balance in the education types a firm possesses would increase the likelihood of having an innovation. There is a bias in the education diversity measure, since it measures diversity within the highly educated group, meaning the employees with a bachelor degree or higher. All employees with a degree below

bachelor are put in a single category. According to the Ostergaard (2002), as a result a higher entropy value can be explained by having a larger share of employees with a higher education and multiple types of higher educated people. Having a higher educated employee alone would be positive for innovation performance, having more different types would increase the likelihood. (Ostergaard, 2002). Firms with a higher share of employees with a higher education and diversity in the types of educations have a higher likelihood of innovating. Although education is essential to human capital, on job training, health care, experience and migration also have great effect on the actual human capital. Growth-oriented strategies moderated the effects of group diversity in level of education on composite bonuses; this type of diversity was more beneficial in department with a strong focus on growth oriented strategies (Bezrukova, 2004). An organization may make an effort to compensate for educational or skill deficiencies of group members by offering specialized training that brings employees up to the required standards (Moskos and Butler, 1996)

Summary of Findings

From the correlation analysis the result shows that the beta () value is significant for all hypotheses (H1, H2, H3 and H4) which show positive relationship between the workforce diversity and performance of the employees. The relationship between employee performance and gender group, age group, ethnicity group, educational background is small, but definite relationship i.e. (R=0.293, 0.397, 0.346 and 0.365 respectively with $p < 0.01$). The regression analysis shows that, the R² figure of the four independent variables is 0.211. These also mean that independent variables (gender, age, ethnicity and educational background) can explain only 21.1% of the variation in dependent variable (employee performance). However, it still leaves 78.9% (100% - 21.1%) unexplained in this research. In other words, there are other additional variables that are important in explaining employee performance that have not been considered in this research.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

The results clearly indicate that it is important for any organization to implement diversity management. The results specifically indicate that high employee performance relates positively with variables such as gender and education background. Therefore, business organizations should start realizing the need to tackle such demographic categories in order to stay ahead of its competitors. Diversifying workers from different education background creates opportunities for greater innovation and more creative solutions to problems. Organizations that view diversity as part of their key strategy rather than a business expense will benefit far greater than the organization that does not and will reap the benefit of cost reduction in attrition and increased revenues to face extensive competition. The diverse workforce is providing a challenge to the organizations. It is very important to know the impact of workforce diversity on employee performance. This paper was undertaken to identify the impact of workforce diversity on employee performance in Stallion Group by taking several independent variables. The theoretical framework has been developed based on the problem statement of the study and by reviewing the literature on workforce diversity & performance link. The data was collected through questionnaires. 80 questionnaires were distributed to different staff of Stallion group of company. S.C. SPSS 20.0 version was used to analyze the correlation and regression among these variables.

The top management should undergo some training on how to leverage on diversity of its workforce. To enhance proper management of diversity, the company must move from its current moderate position, and include diversity in its strategic plan, as resources for organizational effectiveness. Management of Stallion Group of company should consider cultural diversity as a strategic imperative. It is recommended that the organizations should adopt a more inclusive policy of recruiting employees of diverse cultures drawing them from different nationalities in an effort to tap from their strengths and capabilities since cultural diversity appears to be a key factor that could drive organizational performance. Employee exchange programmes are recommended so as to have them exposed to different global cultures. This would help them keep abreast with emerging issues relating to their work, thus making them more adaptive to the changing environment.

The study recommends that management in the Stallion Group Nigeria should conduct regular reviews on their staff establishments in relation to the existing workforce diversities in an effort to establish cultural diversity levels that create synergy for optimum organizational performance. The study also recommends that organizations should develop and inculcate diversity mainstreaming.

We suggest that management of organizations should develop mechanisms that promote cultural diversity in the workplace through effective diversity programs. Regular training on diversity should be conducted among the employees for the purpose of strengthening the wellbeing of the organization. This helps in the development of cohesive teams and greater concentration at work

6.0 Limitation of the study

This research does not consider the other dimensions of diversity like physical ability, sexual orientation, marital status, geographic location & religious affiliation, due to this, the number of independent variables is a limitation of the research.

The focus of this study is the Stallion Group of company which is a multinational company within the private sector of the economy. Human resource practices in private and public sector of the economy may vary greatly especially with respect to issues of cultural diversity. The variation in practice could pose a limitation to the study findings which could not be generalized to apply to all the sectors of the economy.

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